

THE USE OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN THE CLASSROOM

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ANNOTATION

The following article highlights of using project-based learning in the classroom. Author made a imperic research on this issue. The application of the project method in English lessons is being considered language in elementary school. There is one types of projects. It is educational. It is proved that the project method is a method that allows organizing the educational activities of younger schoolchildren, forming universal educational activities, developing the personality of each participant of the project. Special attention is paid to the peculiarities of organizing joint educational activities of students in the project in particular, the organization of group interaction.

KEYWORDS: *educational activity, joint activity, educational project, self-activity, innovative methods.*

INTRODUCTION

A modern elementary school operates according to the Ministry of Preschool and School Education in Uzbekistan, which is based on a system-activity approach [1]. The teacher is faced with the task of organizing educational activities that it would contribute to the development of universal learning activities, the personality of the student. educational activity is primarily a joint activity, as a result of which the maximum activation of students' communicative activity occurs. One of the most effective forms of joint activity is working in groups. According to the new Educational Standard, it is group work that is most effective for achieving educational results, in particular for the formation of communicative universal educational actions. To organize educational activities in English lessons help with temporary educational technologies. In a modern primary school, various teaching technologies are being implemented aimed at the formation of universal educational activities. One of these technologies is the project method. This method originated in the second half of the XIX century in agricultural schools in the USA, then it was transferred to a general educational school. John Dewey, the founder of the method, set out to make the life of the child meaningful, saturated with creative work and significant achievements, suggesting for this purpose "to build learning through its expedient activity, focusing

onhis personal interest and the practical necessity of the acquired knowledge in later life" [2]. A follower of J. Dewey was William Hurd Kilpatrick, who believed that a project is any activity performed "from the bottom of my heart", with a high degree of self-activity by a group of children united at the moment by a common interest. In Uzbekistan the project method has been known since 1990. Then a group of Uzbek teachers under the leadership of S. T. Shatsky introduced it into educational practice. Development of this method in Russian schools is also associated with the name of such teachers as V.N. Shulgin, M. V. Krupenina, B. V. Ignatiev, etc. In the system of domestic school education, it was revived in the early 1990s, which was associated with the introduction of educational technologies in the learning process.

METHODS

By the project we mean the joint educational activity of a teacher and students aimed at solving a specific practical problem and obtaining a product. Projects carried out by younger school children can be divided into two groups: educational and educational [3]. The educational project is aimed at solving subject problems and eliminating educational difficulties. One example of an educational project is the project "I play games, I know English better". While studying the topic "Apartment", fourth graders could not memorize the vocabulary on this topic. They asked the teacher to teach them to memorize English words. We discussed this problem together in the lesson and came to the conclusion that it is easier to remember words in a game situation. It was decided to come up with and independently produce lexical games that would help to memorize words faster and easier. Then the decision was made about working on the project. At the first stage of work on the project, students jointly discussed the topic and the idea of the project. An interesting fact is that all the children took part in the discussion, no one stood aside, the name of the project appeared immediately and did not change during the entire work on it. Also at this stage, the goal was set and the tasks of our work were defined. At the second stage, the planning of joint work took place. It was decided to search for information about what kind of games there are, to get acquainted with the games of the United Kingdom- tania and Russia, come up with games for faster memorization of vocabulary on the topic of "Quart shooting". To do this, the students were divided into groups of 4 people. The division into groups was initiated by the children: the students themselves decided who would work with whom and in which group. Tasks were distributed in groups; for example, one person was looking for information about popular games in the UK, another was getting acquainted with games for children in Uzbekistan, two people were looking for information about what games there are on the Internet, and also talked to adults (parents, teachers) and found out what games they play played in children. The

younger students actively worked and presented all the information they collected. After systematization and analysis of the information, the students decided to make board games that would be in the office in a certain place, and they could be played during recess. The following forms of games were defined: "Domino", "Lotto", "Memory" and "Bingo" games.

At the third stage, the students started making board games. The guys were divided into 4 groups again, each group chose a game and worked on it, projects the students discussed the games together, all groups took part in the discussion of each game. At this stage, the time for this work has been determined. It should be noted that the students independently attracted not only teachers of technology and fine arts to the activity (with them they solved issues on the design of the game, the production of chips and cards), but also their parents, who assisted in the design of materials. Thus, joint activities were organized not only by students with each other, but also by students and teachers, parents. When the games were ready, the groups presented them in class: they told about the game, about how the work went, and also gave the opportunity to play games to students of other groups. At the fourth stage, the presentation of the results of joint activities, we decided on the form of the presentation and decided that it would be a master class. secondly, we discussed the time of the event, prepared a presentation, which we organized as part of the foreign language week for students of grades 3-4. Thus, the peculiarity of the organization of educational activities in projects is that it is a joint activity.

RESULTS

As a result of this activity, subject tasks are solved and educational difficulties are eliminated. There is an opportunity for the realization and development of each student, regardless of his language training and abilities. The main form of organization of such activities is working in groups, which allows you to form a language competence. The division into groups occurs according to the initiative of students, which affects the development of motivation to study the subject. Not only students and teachers can be involved in joint activities, but also parents, teachers of different subject areas. The main task of a teacher in organizing educational activities in a project is to be an assistant, partner and participant in this activity [4]. When working on an educational project, the educational initiative goes beyond the lesson and the program and is embodied in a creative joint product. Let 's give an example of the educational project "Who lives in the tower?". At one of the lessons, after the students told in English about different animals, the teacher formulated a problematic question: "Can different animals live together in one house?". After the discussion, the children came to the conclusion that wild and domestic animals will not be able to live together, predators

with herbivores, too. The students offered many ideas on how to make friends with different animals. After discussing all the ideas, the guys decided to put a spec about the friendly life of various animals in one house. The work on the project lasted one month and passed in several stages. At the first stage, the students jointly discussed the topic and the idea of the project, determined the tasks of working on the project. At the second stage - the stage of planning work on the project - it was decided which animals would live in the same house. To do this, we worked in groups of 4 people. The groups were divided in such a way that each group had students with different language training. Working in a group, students chose animals (3 different animals each), made up stories about them in English, drew and pre they put their own animals. Then they wrote the script of the performance in groups that were formed by the students themselves at their request. Each group came up with its own scenario. After discussion, we chose the most successful one. They showed the script to the head of the school's teaching staff. There was no competition between the groups, as everyone was working on one common project. From the very beginning of the work, the students were focused on the fact that the final assessment would depend on everyone's efforts. In subsequent lessons, the formation of certain speech skills (speaking, listening, reading, writing) is connected moose with a project. While working on the project, the guys used various information from the course of the surrounding world. They exchanged interesting facts that they learned about animals with each other. Moreover, the students themselves selected poems and songs in English for their heroes.

At the third stage, we worked on the production of decorations, masks, and selected the interior. Rehearsals of the play took place after lessons. There were 14 animals living in our miracle house (according to the number of students in the group, everyone got a role). At the fourth stage - the presentation of the project - it was decided to show our performance first-graders of the school. The parents of the "artists" were also invited to the performances. So, the main form of organizing educational activities when working on an educational project is also working in groups. At the same time , groups can for to be trained both on the initiative of younger schoolchildren and from students with different language training. As a result of such activities, students not only receive pre met knowledge, they have personal development, universal educational actions are formed. When using the project method, the role of the teacher also changes. The teacher assumes the role of an organizer of joint activities, a consultant and a colleague in solving the task, obtaining the necessary knowledge and information from various sources, as well as an expert who gives a clear analysis of the results of the completed project.

DISCUSSION

Working on projects in English lessons is offered by all English language teachers starting from the second grade (from the first year of English language training). Here is an example of a number of topics (tasks) of projects. UMK "English with pleasure" by the authors M. Z. Biboletova, O. A. Denisenko, N. N. Trubaneva offers the following topics for projects: a birthday party, a trip to the miracle forest, my family - my wealth. UMK "Forward" (authors - MV Verbitskaya, B. Ebbs, E. Worell, E. Ward) offer the following topics for projects: acquaintance with Australia, a project about dinosaurs, unusual- new animals, we open the world. In the UMK "Milli" by authors S. I. Azarova, E. N. Druzhinina and others, younger schoolchildren are invited to come up with unusual inhabitants of an unusual planet and tell about them, invent and make a musical instrument for the orchestra, make their own translation of the poem "Humpty Dumpty". To see how effectively this method works, for two years in the 3rd grades of the MBOU "Zonalnenskaya SOSH" of the Tomsk region, monitoring was carried out on the following indicators: experience in processing results and presenting their results- tov, the area of preferences in project and research activities, the degree of usefulness of acquired skills, motivation for project and research activities. Monitoring was carried out according to the methodology developed by the Regional Center for the Development of Education (RCRO), "Questionnaire for determining the level of culture of design and research activities. Results of monitoring "Questionnaire for determining the level of culture- design and research activity" in the project. The monitoring results show that the number of students with a high and medium level of culture of design and research activities has increased in all classes. According to the observations of teachers, younger schoolchildren are waiting with great interest for the end of the topic (according to the English Language Curriculum, projects are supposed to be completed at the end of the topic) in order to start working on the project. By the end of the third grade, students. they try to speak as much as possible in the language being studied while working on the project.

CONCLUSION

Summing up all of the above, we can conclude that the project method allows you to organize educational activities both in the classroom and in extracurricular H. N. Plotnikova. The method of projects in teaching English in primary school... activities. Within the framework of this method, students work together with each other, with teachers and parents. All work is initiated by the students themselves, the teacher organizer, consultant and participant of joint activities. The results of the activity in the framework of this method are not only subject knowledge and skills, but also personal achievements: the development of independence, skills of cooperation with adults and

peers, the development of the ability not to create conflicts and find ways out of controversial situations. This method also works for metasubject results: willingness to listen to the interlocutor and conduct a dialogue, development of the ability to express one's opinion and argue one's point of view, active use of speech tools to solve communicative tasks [5].

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